

THE EFFECT OF DOCTOR-PATIENT INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION AND *PATIENT TRUST* ON PATIENT SATISFACTION AT THE HAJJ HOSPITAL IN THE PROVINCE OF SOUTH SULAWESI

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Abstract

Background. Hospitals are health places that can receive many complaints and cases; Sometimes doctors make mistakes in diagnosing diseases, resulting in lawsuits. This can occur due to barriers in communication between doctors and patients as well as a lack of patient trust in health service providers. Building patient trust as a healthcare organization can be accomplished by consistently raising patient satisfaction levels. The primary objective of service providers is to ensure patient satisfaction, as it is anticipated that they will receive repeat business from satisfied clients. Aim. This study aims to analyze the effect of doctor-patient interpersonal communication and patient trust on patient satisfaction at the Haji Hospital Inpatient Installation of South Sulawesi Province. Methods, This type of research is quantitative research using observational studies with a cross-sectional study design. The sample was 400 patients at the Haji Hospital Inpatient Installation of South Sulawesi Province. Results. The findings indicate that the impact of interpersonal communication variables on patient satisfaction is significant, with a value of $0.001 < 0.05$ and a significant effect on patient satisfaction. Similarly, the patient trust variable has a significant value of $0.001 < 0.05$ and a conclusion that it may have a significant effect on patient satisfaction with a value of 38.2%. Conclusion. there is a significant influence between interpersonal communication variables and patient trust on patient satisfaction at the Haji Regional General Hospital, South Sulawesi Province.

Keywords: Interpersonal Communication; Patient Trust; And Patient Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals as health service centers can lead to several complaints and cases that occur, there are several cases of doctors who make mistakes in diagnosing diseases that can lead to lawsuits. This can start due to barriers in patient doctor communication. According to research conducted by the *American Society of Internal Medicine*, good doctor-patient communication has been found to reduce the number of complaints and lawsuits against doctors. (Dewi, 2009).

Doctors are expected to be willing to listen well, pay attention to patient complaints and not show a hasty attitude. The doctor's willingness to provide sufficient time is needed to establish good communication between the doctor and the patient. If the doctor who conducts the examination appears to be in a hurry, and seems reluctant to communicate, the patient will feel reluctant to communicate well with the doctor. Some patients complain about the doctor's service not because of the doctor's ability or expertise, but because they feel that they are not given enough attention. Often patients do not get the opportunity to express what they feel, resulting in patient dissatisfaction. (Riyadi et al., 2020). Research that is in line with this research is research conducted by (Silaen & Alferraly, 2019) shows that there is a significant relationship between doctor-patient communication and patient satisfaction.

In addition to interpersonal communication, the patient doctor who effects patient satisfaction is *patient trust*. *Patient trust* is the key to building *relationship marketing*, and trust itself exists and exists when one party has confidence in the reliability, ability and integrity of work partners (Morgan & Hunt, 1994). As a healthcare institution, creating patient trust can be built through continuous improvement of patient satisfaction. Research conducted by Chang et al., 2013 showed that trust has a direct and significant effect on patient satisfaction. The choice of a particular hospital as a referral indicates the patient's *trust* in the hospital or doctor serving at the hospital concerned.

Patient satisfaction is the main goal of service providers, because if they can serve patients well, it is hoped that patients will return to the service provider. Patient satisfaction can be realized by meeting the expectations and needs of patients (Raheem et al., 2014).

Hajj Hospital is one of the class B hospitals owned by the government of South Sulawesi. the hospital is a hospital with very good religious nuances. based on the patient satisfaction index report of hajj hospital of south sulawesi province above, shows that the community satisfaction index report for the last three years has fluctuated in 2017 by 77.8% in 2018 by 85.4% and in 2019 by 85% with an average of 82.73%. as well as drill data in the inpatient installation for the last three years decreased from 2017 which is 60%, 2018 which is 52% and 2019 which is 50%. Inpatient visit data in the last 3 years has fluctuated, namely in 2017 it had 7820 inpatient visit data, in 2018 it decreased to 6881 inpatient visits and in 2019 it rose again to 8502 inpatient visit data.

Researchers chose the variables of patient doctor interpersonal communication, *patient trust* and patient satisfaction based on the problem data obtained, which is quite large, namely the low patient satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province and the results of previous research conducted by (Kurtz, 2021) shows that patient-doctor interpersonal communication has a significant effect on patient satisfaction. Research results (Liu et al., 2021) shows that *patient trust* has a significant effect on patient satisfaction. Likewise, similar research was conducted by (Yudia et al., 2019) the results showed that doctor-patient interpersonal had a significant effect on patient satisfaction at RSUD A.W. Sjahranie Samarinda. Similar research was conducted by (Imran & Ramli, 2019) shows that high patient satisfaction can increase patient trust.

Seeing the problems related to patient satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province and the importance of paying attention to patient-doctor interpersonal communication and patient *trust value* in hospitals, researchers are interested in conducting research on "The effect of patient-doctor interpersonal communication and *patient trust* on patient satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and research design

This study was conducted at the Hajj Hospital Hospital of South Sulawesi Province. The type of research used was analytic observational with *cross sectional* design.

Population and sample

The population was all patients who performed services at the Hajj Hospital Inpatient Installation of South Sulawesi Province with a sample size of 400 patients.

Data collection method

The instrument used in data collection is a questionnaire that has been tested for validity and reliability, the independent variable is Interpersonal Communication and *Patient Trust* while the dependent variable is Patient Satisfaction.

Data analysis

Univariate analysis was conducted to obtain an overview of the research problem by describing each variable used in the study and the characteristics of the respondents. Univariate analysis consists of descriptive analysis of respondent characteristics, descriptive analysis of research variables and crosstabulation analysis between dependent and independent variables. Bivariate analysis was conducted to see the relationship between two variables, namely between the independent variable and the dependent variable with the statistical test used was the Chi Square test. Multivariate analysis is multiple logistic regression with the enter method.

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Based on Respondent Characteristics in Patients at the Inpatient Installation of the Hajj Provincial Hospital of South Sulawesi in 2023

Characteristics	Research Sample	
	N	%
Age		
<20 Years	96	24.0
20-35 Years	134	33.5
36-45 Years	46	11.5
>45 Years	124	31.0
Total	400	100.0
Gender		
male	157	39.25
Female	243	60.75
Total	400	100.0
Last Education		
Elementary School	29	7.2
Junior High School	45	11.3
Senior High School	135	33.8
Diploma	12	3.0
Bachelor Degree	122	30.5
Master Degree	27	6.8
More	30	7.5
Total	400	100.0
Jobs		
Students	74	18.5
College Student	40	10.0
Self-employed	41	10.3
Private Employee	52	13.0
Public Servant	41	10.3
Not Working	16	4.0
More	136	34.0

Total	400	100.0
Hospitalization Class		
Class I	44	11.0
Class II	151	37.8
Class III	121	30.3
VIP	84	21.0
Total	400	100.0
Distance		
<5 KM	299	74.8
>5 KM	101	25.3
Total	400	100.0
Hospital visits		
>1 Time	347	86.8
Infinity	53	13.3
Total	400	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2023

The table above shows that most respondents are at the age level of 26-35 years, namely 134 respondents (33.5%). Judging from gender, most of them are female, namely 243 respondents (60.75%). Based on the latest education, most respondents have a high school education, namely 135 respondents (33.8%). Judging from occupation, most respondents were in the other occupation category, namely 136 respondents (34.0%). Judging from the class of care, most respondents were in class II care, namely 151 respondents (37.8). Based on the distance from the hospital, most respondents had a distance of <5 KM, namely 299 respondents (74.8%). While from the number of visits to the hospital, most respondents had >1 visit, namely 347 respondents (86.8%).

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Research Variables in Patients at the Inpatient Installation of the Hajj Provincial Hospital of South Sulawesi in 2023

Variables	Research Sample	
	N	%
Interpersonal Communication		
Good	218	54.5
Not so good	182	45.5
Total	400	100.0
Patient Trust		
Good	237	59.3
Less Good	163	40.8
Total	400	100.0
Patient Satisfaction		
Satisfied	227	56.8
Less Satisfied	173	43.3
Total	400	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on the table above, most respondents stated that they were in the good Interpersonal Communication category of 54.5%, in the good *Patient Trust* category of 59.3% and in the good Patient Satisfaction category of 56.8%. The *cut of point* for determining good and bad criteria for good interpersonal communication variables ≥ 70 and bad < 70 , good *patient trust* variables ≥ 20 and bad < 20 and patient satisfaction variables satisfied ≥ 92.5 and dissatisfied < 92.5 .

Table 3: The Relationship between Interpersonal Communication and Patient Satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province in 2023

Interpersonal Communication	Patient Satisfaction				Total		P
	Satisfied		Less Satisfied		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	212	97.2%	6	2.8%	218	100.0	0.001
Not so good	15	8.2%	167	91.8%	182	100.0	
Total	227	56.8%	173	43.3%	400	100.0	

Table 4: Relationship between Patient Trust and Patient Satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province in 2023

Patient Trust	Patient Satisfaction				Total		P
	Satisfied		Less Satisfied		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	218	92.0%	19	8.0%	237	100.0	0.001
Not so good	9	5.5%	154	94.5%	163	100.0	
Total	227	56.8%	173	43.3%	400	100.0	

Table 3 shows the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that the relationship between interpersonal communication variables and *patient trust* on patient satisfaction in the Inpatient Installation of the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province in 2023. The results of bivariate analysis with the Pearson correlation test show that there is a relationship between interpersonal variables and *patient* satisfaction with a p value = 0.001 and *patient trust* on patient satisfaction with a p value = 0.001.

Table 5: The influence of patient doctor interpersonal communication variables and patient trust on patient satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province in 2023.

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.046	.031		1.504	.133
Interpersonal communication	.580	.034	.583	17.308	.001
<i>Patient_trust</i>	.385	.034	.382	11.334	.001

Table 5 shows that the statistical test used is logistic regression with the enter method. The effect of interpersonal communication variables on patient satisfaction is 0.001 < 0.05 with a value of 58.3%, so it can be concluded that interpersonal communication variables have a significant effect on patient satisfaction and for *patient trust* variables of 0.001 < 0.05 with a value of 38.2%, so it can be that *patient trust* variables have a significant effect on patient satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the study above (Table 3) shows that of the 400 respondents with good Interpersonal Communication and satisfied patient satisfaction, 212 respondents (97.2%) and as many as 6 respondents (2.8%) had less satisfied patient satisfaction. Meanwhile, with poor Interpersonal Communication and Satisfied Patient Satisfaction, there were 15 respondents (8.2%) and 167 respondents (91.8%) who had poor Interpersonal Communication and Dissatisfied Patient Satisfaction.

The statistical test results obtained a p value = 0.001, because the p value $< \alpha = 0.001 < 0.05$ this means that there is a statistically significant relationship between Interpersonal Communication and Patient Satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province.

The results of the study above (Table 4) also show that of the 400 respondents with good *Patient Trust* with Satisfied Patient Satisfaction were 218 respondents (92.0%) and as many as 19 respondents (8.0%) who had Less Satisfied Patient Satisfaction. Meanwhile, with poor *Patient Trust* and Satisfied Patient Satisfaction, there were 9 respondents (5.5%) and 154 respondents (94.5%) with poor *Patient Trust* and Unsatisfied Patient Satisfaction.

The statistical test results obtained a p value = 0.001, because the p value $< \alpha = 0.001 < 0.05$ this means that there is a statistically significant relationship *Patient Trust* on Patient Satisfaction at the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province.

Table 5 shows that the influence of the Doctor Patient interpersonal communication variable on patient satisfaction is $0.001 < 0.05$ with a value of 58.3%, so it can be concluded that the Doctor Patient interpersonal communication variable has a significant effect on patient satisfaction, for the influence of the patient *trust* variable on patient satisfaction is of $0.001 < 0.05$ with a value of 38.2%, so it can be that the *patient trust* variable has a significant effect on patient satisfaction. It can be concluded that there is a significant influence between interpersonal communication variables and *patient trust* on patient satisfaction at the Haji Regional General Hospital, South Sulawesi Province ".

According to (Williams et al., 1998) as a doctor certainly cannot be separated from the communication process with patients. The effectiveness of communication between doctors and patients is needed to build patient trust in the healing process. Among several communications, interpersonal communication is one of the most effective communications in building relationships with patients.

Doctors are expected to be willing to listen well, pay attention to patient complaints and not show a hasty attitude. The doctor's willingness to provide sufficient time is needed to establish good communication between the Doctor and Patient. If the doctor conducting the examination seems hurried, and seems reluctant to communicate, the patient will feel reluctant to communicate well with the doctor. Some patients complain about the doctor's service not because of the doctor's ability or expertise, but because they feel less cared for. Often patients do not get the opportunity to express what they feel, resulting in patient dissatisfaction. (Muhammad Hafidz Riyadi et al., 2020).

Some of the reasons that cause patients not to return to the hospital are 1% due to death, 3% due to moving residence, 5% due to satisfaction with other companies, 9% due to competitors' persuasion, 14% due to dissatisfaction with the product and 68% due to poor service quality (Tiara et al., 2013). The satisfaction in question is a situation where the patient's wants, expectations and needs for services are met. Satisfaction assessment includes the ability of officers to provide services to patients quickly, accurately, reliably, and able to build good relationships with patients. Patients are often dissatisfied with the quality and amount of information received from health workers, this can be seen from research (Tiara et al., 2013) that 35% - 40% of patients are not satisfied communicating with doctors.

Good trust is a recognition and appreciation from consumers of the usefulness of the product or service provided by the service provider in accordance with consumer expectations. Wulandari et al., (2020) also revealed that trust exists if customers believe that service providers can be trusted and are able to realize the commitments that have been made, and have a high degree of integrity.

To create *trust* from patients, medical personnel must be able to minimize the occurrence of work errors during action or patient care. *Trust* allows hospital managers to predict consumer attitudes, reduce the level of sensitivity to errors, increase patient value. Furthermore, *trust* can also reduce costs to increase patient satisfaction and maintain long-term relationships with patients. (Afrizal & Suhardi, 2018).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results showed that interpersonal communication and *patient trust had* a significant effect on patient satisfaction at the Inpatient Installation of the Hajj Hospital of South Sulawesi Province. Interpersonal communication is an activity carried out in everyday life, and is a way to convey and receive thoughts, information, ideas, feelings, and even one's emotions, to the point of reaching the same understanding between the communicator and the communicant. Contextually, interpersonal communication is described as a communication between two or fewer individuals, who interact with each other, giving feedback to each other. However, providing a contextual definition is not enough to describe interpersonal communication because every interaction between one individual and another is different.

It is hoped that these results can be used as a reference that contributes, especially hospital quality. For hospital management must continue to pay attention to interpersonal communication in order to improve the relationship between patient doctors, so as to increase patient satisfaction to visit again to utilize the health service facilities provided by the hospital. For hospital management, it is necessary to make improvements in terms of patient satisfaction in the Inpatient installation of the Hajj Regional General Hospital of South Sulawesi Province.

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